

Rice cultivars with disease resistance

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Four hundred and ninety-one rice cultivars were screened under natural field infection during kharif 1980 for resistance to the following rice diseases: brown spot at 12 locations, bacterial blight at 15, and tungro at 5.

The cultivars in the table were found resistant or moderately resistant to those diseases at Coimbatore as well as in other locations. ■

Cultivars found resistant at Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Disease	Designation	Cross	Disease severity grade at Coimbatore ^a (0-7 scale)
Brown spot	IET7137	MTU15/Waikoku	1
	IET7145	T141/Baok//T141	1
	IET6753	Hema/RPW6-13	3
	IET7134	Shirauni/Goenchiew	3
	IET7117	Ratna/TKM6	
	IET6880	RP31-49-2/LMN	3
Bacterial blight	IET6361	IR24/TKM6	3
	ET5953	CR161-42-16 (Vijaya/W12708)	3
Tungro	IET6268	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	3

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant.

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at CRRI, India

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The life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* collected and reared locally were tested on seedlings of 10 rice varieties in the CRRI greenhouse, Cuttack, India, 22 November to 14 December 1978. To study the insect's life span 400 adult insects — 20 females and 20 males for each variety — were given an acquisition access time of 2 days on tungro-diseased plants. The insects survived 1 to 22 days on 1-week-old seedlings. Their life span averaged 8.5 days — 8.9 days for female insects and 8.0 days for the male.

On the basis of average insect life span, Ptb 18, IR34, and Gam Pai 30-12-15 were more resistant than the other varieties in the test (see table).

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at CRRI, India, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Ambemohar 159	21	11.9 a	44	1	1.0	11	0.44	1.00
TN1	18	11.6 a	81	4	1.8	34	1.44	1.77
Pankhari 203	22	11.6 a	25	3	1.4	8	0.31	1.25
IR26	19	10.1 ab	84	3	1.6	34	1.38	1.63
Habiganj DW8	22	9.9 ab	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latisail	21	8.9 b	69	5	2.0	31	1.41	2.05
Kataribhog	22	8.8 b	6	1	1.0	1	0.06	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	13	4.8 c	50	3	1.7	23	0.81	1.63
IR34	14	4.7 c	59	3	1.8	28	1.08	1.74
Ptb 18	5	2.6 d	9	1	1.0	3	0.09	1.00
Max or av	22	8.5	43	5	1.3	17	0.70	1.31

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

The tungro transmission differed remarkably among the varieties. About 18% of 1,251 seedlings inoculated by 320 viruliferous insects became infected. But the insects were unable to transmit the tungro virus to Habiganj DW8 and were

poor in transmitting it to Kataribhog, Ptb 18, and Pankhari 203 (see table). Those varieties were probably more resistant to tungro than the other six in the test. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Rice yield losses due to gall midge infestation in northern Thailand

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has been an endemic pest of rice in northern

Thailand for half a century. Although insecticides and resistant varieties have proved effective for gall midge control, they are not adopted widely by farmers.

An experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai Province, to determine if gall midge damage would reduce the rice yield and

whether insecticide control was economically feasible.

Four rice varieties were studied: RD 1 (susceptible), Leaug-Laung (local), and Dok-Ma-Li 105 and Niew-San-Pa-Tong (recommended traditional). The experiment used a split plot and was replicated three times. The main plot was

Infestation and yield losses caused by rice gall midge on 4 rice varieties at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, Thailand, 1979.

Treatment		Damaged tillers (%)		Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
Rice variety	Insecticide ^a	30 DT	55 DT	55 DT			
Leaung-Laung	treated	0.9	1.8	7.1	4.5	2.909	–
Leaung-Laung	untreated	2.4	25.0	8.4	3.1	1.951	32.9
RD1	treated	1.4	1.0	11.4	5.5	2.323	–
RD1	untreated	3.5	21.5	12.0	4.4	1.866	19.7
Dok-Ma-Li 105	treated	0.6	0.4	10.1	5.7	2.033	–
Dok-Ma-Li 105	untreated	0.9	19.2	10.7	4.9	1.828	10.1
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	treated	1.3	2.2	7.9	4.6	2.740	–
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	untreated	2.3	26.5	9.7	4.4	2.522	7.9

^aFor gall midge control, carbofuran 3% G was applied to treated plots at the rate of 1 kg a.i./ha 2 times – 20 and 40 days after transplanting (DT).

divided into 4 equal subplots where the 4 rice varieties were transplanted at 3 seedlings/hill. Each replication consisted of 2 main plots, treated and untreated. The treated plots received carbofuran 3% G at 1 kg a.i./ha 2 times, 20 and 40 days after transplanting (DT).

The percentages of damaged tillers caused by the rice gall midge among the

4 untreated rice varieties were at the same level (see table). Carbofuran at 1 kg a.i./ha was effective for gall midge control. The damaged tillers for the treated plots averaged 1.4% at 55 DT. The average number of tillers per hill was higher in the untreated plots because gall midge infestation induced tillering. However, the number of panicles per hill

and grain yield were higher in the treated plots. The percentages of yield losses due to gall midge damage varied. Leaung-Laung showed the greatest yield loss, 32.9%, when 25% of the tillers were damaged, but Niew-San-Pa-Tong had only 7.9% loss at the same level of damage. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Effect of submergence tolerance screening during rapid generation advance on heading duration and productivity

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Heavy rainfall or sudden flooding often causes submergence of tropical rice. The flooding generally occurs during the early growth stages and seriously hampers crop growth.

Previous studies have shown that lines can be screened for submergence tolerance during rapid generation advance (RGA). This report covers the effect of early, total submergence on growth duration and productivity.

Seeds of 7 rice varieties were presoaked and sown in “square” pots (5.1 cm x 5 cm) and vials (3 cm diameter x 4.5 cm height). Only one plant was placed in each container. Ten days after sowing, the seedlings were subjected to 7 days of total submergence. The surviving plants were kept under normal greenhouse

conditions, and the heading dates of each variety were recorded. The mature panicles were harvested and the percentage of seed fertility was recorded.

The same procedures were followed with a control group under normal greenhouse conditions.

Abnormality in flowering and a high degree of spikelet sterility were observed in both the control and submerged plants in the vials. These results were anticipated because of the small amount of soil in the vials and the nutritional

requirements for normal plant growth. The results from the “square” pots are in the table.

The heading duration did not vary greatly between submergence-tolerant varieties. But 3 new semidwarf varieties susceptible to submergence showed 5- to 10-day delays in heading because of early submergence.

Spikelet sterility showed little change in tolerant varieties. In semidwarf varieties, however, change was conspicuous, ranging from 20 to 44

Mean heading duration and spikelet sterility of 7 varieties submerged at seedling stage.

Variety	Survival (%)	Heading duration (days)		Seed sterility (%)	
		Control	Submerged	Control	Submerged
Thavalu 15134	100	68	66	18	28
Thavalu 15235	100	63	65	26	26
FR13A	100	75	74	20	15
KDML 105	50	68	64	30	42
IR38	17	89	94	40	60
IR42	50	73	80	43	80
IR8	38	81	91	13	57
Mean		74	76	27	44
SEM ±			1.5		5.7
Calculated “t”			2.6**		3.1**

** Significant at 0.1 0 level.